

MANUFACTURING OF CERAMIC PREFORMS FOR ALMMC

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Abstract: Aluminum Metal Matrix Composites (AlMMC) is an important class of composite materials. AlMMC's has been gaining more interest and acceptance during the past 30 years. A sub-category of this material class is Discontinuous Reinforced Aluminum (DRA). These AlMMC materials contain an aluminum matrix reinforced with ceramic particles, whiskers, or short fibers. The DRA AlMMC has been successfully used in the aerospace, automotive, electronic packaging, and recreational product markets. The DRA AlMMC is an interesting material because it offers a unique set of materials characteristics. These characteristics include low density; higher wear resistance than steel, a coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) that can be tailored and finally high stiffness, on the order of titanium. The process of making DRA AlMMC components includes the manufacture of a ceramic preform followed by the infiltration of the preform with molten aluminum alloy. As interesting as these materials properties are however, these materials have only been used in niche applications.

One of the major barriers that limited the growth of the DRA AlMMC market is the inability to obtain reliable, high quality, cost effective source of ceramic preforms. Traditional ceramic forming methods include slip casting, uni-axial pressing, and cold iso-static pressing. Each of these processes is well established in the ceramic forming industry and each offers its own set of unique advantages and disadvantages with respect to DRA AlMMC preform manufacture. However these traditional forming methods do not offer the ability to produce high volume, complex shape, near net shape components. The Springboard CIM process is capable of meeting and exceeding these requirements. It also allows one the ability to design components with multiple materials in one component, and a host of unique materials microstructural features.

To date, the typical CIM process has been used with limited success due to both the poor economics and inability to manufacture large (i.e. larger than a golf ball) complex shape (three dimensional), high quality preforms. The economics are limited by the debinding stage. Namely, unless one can injection mold a preform component, place it on a plate or setter plate and subsequently debind and sinter it in the same operation without handling, dangerous solvents etc., it is very difficult to envision that this process will ever become a viable option for manufacturing high volume, complex shape DRA AlMMC preforms. Springboard CIM has identified the needs of this industry and has developed a process that is robust, cost efficient, and last but not least, capable of meeting the high quality standards required to move this industry forward. In this paper, we will review the Springboard CIM process and describe the advantages that this process has to offer over the existing CIM technologies. A detailed discussion of the Springboard CIM materials, equipment, processing conditions, and dimensional tolerances will be presented.

KEY WORDS: Metal matrix composites, Ceramic preforms, Ceramic injection molding

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic injection molding (CIM) has been the focus of much effort as a manufacturing method capable of producing very complex ceramic components in high volumes. However, in the past the expensive and/or long debinding times have made this process too expensive to consider for the mass production of AIMMC preforms. The collaborative effort of Springboard CIM, Solar Atmospheres, Moldmaster Engineering, and Caropreso Associates has finally resolved this technical hurdle. Combining the 18 years CIM experience of Springboard and the 30+ years of Solar Atmospheres, we have developed a practical and efficient debinding process that will open the doors of CIM to myriad companies who would have never considered it before. Now complex ceramic preform components of a wide range of sizes can be manufactured to exacting tolerances without the need for high labor rates, long debinding times, cost prohibitive equipment, or potentially harmful packing medias and solvents.

CERAMIC FORMING METHODS

Engineering ceramic materials are most known for their intrinsic resistance to heat, corrosion, wear, and electrically insulating properties. Thus they are commonly used in more extreme applications where both metal and plastic materials are less likely to survive. But the very material properties that make these ceramics attractive for more extreme applications also make them more expensive to manufacture. For example, if one is considering a complex three-dimensional ceramic preform component in a moderate to high volume (e.g. greater than say 10,000 units per month) application that also requires close dimensional tolerances (e.g. ± 0.001 " per inch), then the manufacturing costs can be quite high. These parts are very expensive due to the high cost of machining hard materials.

Current forming methods for producing complex shape components include slip casting, cold isostatic pressing, die pressing, extrusion, and ceramic injection molding. Of these methods, CIM is the only one that offers the potential to produce complex 3-D shaped ceramic preform components in a rapid, automated, and cost efficient manner. The CIM process involves four process stages: Compounding, Injection Molding, Debinding, and Sintering.

THE CIM PROCESS/COMPOUNDING

In the first stage, the compounding of the raw materials (ceramic powders and binders) provides a homogeneous dispersion of all of the individual components. The selection of the ceramic powder depends upon the end product application and associated material requirements. For example, coarse-grained materials (75-100 micron) are used for refractory fused silica casting cores used in the investment casting of super-alloy turbine blades. Conversely, fine grain silicon nitride ceramic (sub-micron) materials are used in the fabrication of ceramic turbine blades. Ceramic powders are initially agglomerated. One of the primary goals of the compounding stage is complete de-agglomeration of the ceramic powders.

De-agglomeration is essential for two reasons. First, ceramic agglomerates act as minute porous sponges that trap the binder. The function of the binder component is to carry the ceramic particles into the mold during the injection molding stage. If agglomerates exist in the feedstock (compounded material), the material will not exhibit the optimum flow characteristics necessary for molding complex shaped components. Secondly, agglomerates act as flaw centers in the final sintered components, thereby reducing the strength and reliability of the final product. The strength of a ceramic component is determined by its largest flaw, or "weakest link." Springboard carefully engineers both the ceramic-binder compatibility and the mixing process to ensure the highest degree of material dispersion. Figure 1 shows the difference between an agglomerated and deagglomerated system. In this case, a chemical means was used to de-agglomerate Silicon powder used in the generation of reaction bonded silicon nitride parts. The careful engineering of both the chemistry and mixing process ensures the highest quality microstructure, which in turn produces a final product with the highest degree of reliability.

The choice of binder chemistry for the CIM process has been a subject of great interest since CIM's inception in the 1940s. The purpose of the binder phase is to form a liquid media for the ceramic powders to be carried into the mold during the injection stage. The criterion for the binder phase includes the compatibility and non-reactivity with the ceramic particles, the proper flow characteristics, and the ability to burn-out cleanly and easily during the binder removal stage. Both the choice of binder and method of binder removal are two of the most critical aspects of the CIM process.

THE CIM PROCESS/INJECTION MOLDING

After the material has been compounded, it is pelletized to form the feedstock for the injection-molding machine. In most cases, a thermoplastic binder is used for the CIM process. A reciprocating screw is used to convey and melt, via shear heating, the CIM feedstock to form a shot. The shot is defined as the amount of material necessary to fill the injection mold, sprue, and runner system. After the shot has been generated, the screw serves as a ram that forces the molten material into a cooled mold. At this point, the material solidifies and takes the shape of the mold. Once the mold has been filled, the pressure inside causes the material to become packed. During the packing stage, the material continues to cool, shrink, and solidify. Then it is strong enough to be ejected from the mold and the cycle is repeated. The injection molding process parameters include temperature (both mold and material), injection pressure, injection rate, and cooling time.

The cycle time is dictated by the thickest part cross section. For a typical part (0.125-0.250 inches thick), the cycle time is approximately one minute. The material is in the cooling phase for approximately 80-90% of that time. Increasing the number of cavities in the mold and using multiple molds in one machine can increase the throughput dramatically. In the plastics industry, it is common to have molds with 8, 16, 32, or even 64 cavities. If one then uses a rotary machine with 8 molds, 7,680 parts per hour (e.g. 16 cavities x 60 shots per hour x 8 molds) can be injection molded. It is this type of manufacturing throughput that makes the CIM process extremely useful for high volume applications.

THE CIM PROCESS/DEBINDING

After the parts have been injection molded, they are debound and later sintered. The most common method of debinding CIM components is pyrolysis in a powder bed. Here, the green (as molded) parts are carefully placed in a sagger (an open ceramic box) which contains ceramic powder, as known as packing media. The characteristics of the packing media are such that it allows the CIM component to be supported during the debinding process. This powder also serves as a wicking media to facilitate the binder removal. The combination of a slow heating rate and wicking causes the binder to be removed from the CIM component. The mechanisms that take place during the debinding are complex. They include melting, boiling, wicking, and pyrolysis. The cycle time to complete this stage depends upon an number of variables, including the type of binder used, the "wicking" power of the packing media, the size of the CIM component, and the heating rate. A typical debinding schedule may involve numerous ramps and soaks at select temperatures to achieve proper debinding. The degree of debinding is also a function of the aforementioned factors. In practice, one tries to remove the optimum amount of binder so the material does not to become too fragile to handle.

In the case of components with varying cross sectional areas, sections that are thin will contain less binder than the thicker sections. In these cases, a delicate balance must be met so the thinner areas are not too fragile and the thicker sections don't contain too much binder. If this occurs, the brown (debound) part will either break during handling or result in bubbles and/or lamination during sintering. Assuming an optimum cycle has been developed, each brown component must be carefully excavated from the sagger,

cleansed of residual powder, and prepared for sintering. This time-consuming debinding process is extremely labor intensive and inefficient in respect to furnace packing density. Also, it often results in high reject rates due to operator mishandling. However, this practice is still widely used in the CIM industry.

The second most common method of debinding is one in which the molded CIM components are immersed in a solvent bath, which serves to dissolve the soluble binder component. In these systems, the binder is usually composed of two discreet phases: one that is soluble in the solvent and another that is not. The solvent can be organic or water based, but in either case, processing the solvent after the components have been debound can be problematic, and often calls for special environmental precautions.

A third method of debinding is called vacuum debinding. In this method, the debinding and sintering can take place in one furnace. The debinding occurs through boiling point suppression and the evaporation of the binders at temperatures below that which would take place at atmospheric pressure. The advantage of this process is that it can be conducted without the need for packing medias, solvents, and extensive labor. It also utilizes the optimum loading density of the debinding/sintering oven. The primary disadvantage is the expensive design and construction of a vacuum tight furnace and the collection and isolation of the debinding products.

Perhaps the simplest debinding method is drying. Binders based on agar and water have also been developed for CIM. In this case, the part is simply dried using conventional drying methods. After the water has been removed, a small percentage of the agar remains and leaves the components extremely rigid and easily machined. This process is relatively simple, non-toxic, and often inexpensive. Unfortunately, it results in a lack of green strength and rigidity for CIM components; so complex three-dimensional green components require special handling equipment. Another factor to consider is the storage and environmental control of the feedstock material. Since these binders are primarily based on water, the humidity in which the material is being processed and stored must be carefully controlled in order to maintain the proper binder level. Finally, these materials can be quite aggressive towards molding machine components, like screws, barrels, and check rings.

The last class of debinding is based on sublimation. In this case, freeze driers are used to sublime high vapor pressure organic binders at or near liquid nitrogen temperatures. Here the components are injection molded into molds that are also at or near liquid nitrogen temperatures. The parts are then carefully and swiftly transferred to freezers and stored. After enough components have been molded, racks of parts are placed in a freeze drier, which controls the vacuum level and temperature to carefully remove the binder via sublimation. The advantage of this process is the ability to debind rather large cross sectional area components and the efficient utilization of furnace packing density. The disadvantages of this process are the special equipment requirements needed to handle and process extremely cold components and the handling and recycling of the sublimed binder phase.

SUMMARY - SOLVING THE DEBINDING DILEMMA

Having reviewed the various debinding methods, it is clear that debinding is the limiting stage in the CIM process. To date, there has been no single debinding method that allows manufacturers to take full advantage of CIM's vast potential. The ideal CIM process would be one where the molded components can be placed on trays, stacked efficiently, placed in a simple, cost effective furnace and debound and sintered without the need for packing medias, solvents, or expensive furnace equipment requirements. Today, CIM components are limited to very few applications. Usually CIM components are no larger than

a golf ball and have as thin a cross sectional area as possible. Larger parts can be made for special applications where long debinding times, high labor rates, expensive binders and debinding equipment can be justified. But the most widespread use of CIM is for relatively small components that are easy and cost effective to debind.

Through the collaborative efforts of Springboard CIM, Solar Atmospheres, Moldmaster Engineering, and Caropreso Associates, an efficient process has been developed for debinding and sintering CIM components of virtually any size, shape, or complexity. This can be done using inexpensive binder materials to injection mold components in a practical manufacturing environment with relatively inexpensive debinding and sintering equipment. In our process, the molded components are placed on trays in an inexpensive inert atmosphere debind/sintering furnace. The debinding process has been designed such that approximately 60-70 % of the binder is removed from the component by a simple ramp/soak temperature cycle. The debinding times are measured in hours rather than days. After the components are debound, they can be directly sintered in the same furnace. This occurs without the need for special binder traps since the binders are pyrolyzed insitu during the sintering operation in an air atmosphere.

Some of the components that are possible through this method are shown in the Figures 2-6. Like in any debinding process, thicker cross sections lead to longer debinding schedules. However, our debinding/sintering timeframes make our process a viable option for those who are considering parts of larger size and a higher degree of complexity.

Another advantage of our process is the ability to injection mold complex hollow shapes, foamed microstructures, and components that contain multiple materials in one component. Examples of these can be seen in figures 7-9. We strongly feel that this set of tools is truly unique and offers distinct advantages over existing CIM systems. In turn, these advantages afford us the ability to provide our customers with unique, yet practical solutions for their ever-increasing stringent material and product requirements.

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Figure 1: These images show the effect of surfactants (surface-active-agents) upon the de-agglomeration of a silicon (Si) powder suspension in mineral oil (a room temperature analog of a CIM binder). In Figure 1a, the Si powders in the “as received” condition are highly agglomerated. By incorporating an effective surfactant (Figure 1b), a high degree of Si powder dispersion is the result.

Figure 2: This 5 x 11 x 0.125 inch test plate is used to generate test samples for the development of silicon carbide metal matrix composite thermal management package materials.

Figure 3: This figure shows the degree of distortion that can take place in a CIM test bar if the debinding process is not performed properly.

Figure 4: Even if the exterior of the debound and sintered CIM part appears homogeneous and defect-free, care must be taken to ensure that the interior is also homogeneous. The test bar on the left shows no evidence of surface defects but the interior has lamination type defects present. This was a result of sub-optimum debinding. Only through the careful understanding of the debinding mechanisms and the control of the debinding conditions can the part microstructure be thoroughly optimized. This attention to detail is critical for ensuring the quality and performance requirements of the final component.

Figure 5: These electrical components were molded from 55 volume percent silicon carbide to demonstrate the detail and degree of complexity that is possible with the Springboard CIM process.

Figure 6: This figure shows a sample electrical cover molded in 60 volume percent silicon carbide. This part photo speaks to the level of complexity and detail that can be achieved with this material and process.

Figure 7: Complex internal passages can be manufactured in CIM preforms using low pressure injection molding methods.

Figure 8: This is a bi-material plastic part cross section. In this case, there are two materials, one black (interior) and one white (exterior). The same process is under evaluation

for functionally gradient materials using two dissimilar ceramic preform materials. Note, each ruled line is 0.010 inches.

Figure 9: The Springboard CIM process can also produce controlled porosity ceramic preforms. This may have applications in energy absorbing and/or weight sensitive applications where very low solids loadings are required. Note each ruled line is 0.010 inches.